

THE ANALYSIS OF THE AVAILABLE CONDITIONS FOR DELIVERING GOODS INTERNATIONALLY BY RAIL

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АННОТАЦИЯ В данной статье проанализированы внешние торговые связи Узбекистана и существующие условия на транспортном рынке при доставке грузов по международным направлениям. Также определены стратегические направления формирования железнодорожных сетей с учетом увеличения грузопотока в будущем.

Ключевые слова: транспортный рынок, международный транспортный коридор, экспортные и транзитные грузы, железнодорожный транспорт.

ANNOTATION This article analyzes the existing conditions in the transportation market of Uzbekistan for delivering goods in foreign trade relations and international directions. Additionally, strategic directions were identified for the development of railway networks, considering the expected increase in freight

Keywords: the transportation market, international transportation routes, export and transit cargoes, railway transportation.

Introduction

External relations in delivering goods and their timely delivery play a significant role. Therefore, in developing our economy, the transportation of corridor cargoes plays a crucial role today.

On May 12, 1996, Uzbekistan's active participation in the utilization of the Tejen-Serakhs-Mashhad railway, with a length of 320 km, marked a significant advancement in the development of international transportation routes (including changing the gauge from 1435 mm to 1520 mm). A new transcontinental route was

opened through Iran and Turkey, connecting the Central Asian states to the global market. That same year, leaders of Uzbekistan, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Turkmenistan signed agreements on “Coordinating Railway Transport Activities” and “Regulating Transit Cargo Transportation among Member States” in the city of Serakhs.

In May 2005, the completion of the construction of the Bafq-Mashhad railway line (linking Tehran) in Erond reduced the distance to the Bandar-Abbas port to less than 800 km. In September 1998, with the initiative of Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Uzbekistan, as well as with the support of the European Union, the international conference “TRASECA - Reconstruction of the Historic Silk Road” was held in Baku. During this conference, leaders from 12 countries, including Uzbekistan, signed the "Basic Multilateral Agreement on the Development of the Europe-Caucasus-Asia Corridor" and various technical applications were signed to update regulations and documents for international railway transportation, international road transportation, international freight forwarding, and customs procedures, marking a significant milestone in the cooperation.

The Europe-Caucasus-Asia (TRACECA) transport corridor is a network of railways and maritime routes connecting Europe to the Central Asian republics via the Caucasus and the Caspian Sea. TRACECA was established with the aim of developing trade relations between Europe and Asia, facilitating the relocation of major cargo flows from Asia to Europe, and vice versa, as well as promoting the placement of production facilities in Asia and consumers in Europe.

The distance along the TRACECA route from Yokohama, the largest port in Western Europe (including Rotterdam, Hamburg, Antwerp, and others), via the main transoceanic route, is more than twice as long. On June 18, 2003, in Tehran (Iran), the leaders of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, and the Islamic Republic of Iran signed the “Agreement on Creating an International Trans-Afghan Transport Corridor,” which shortened the distance for transporting international trade cargoes to Iranian ports by 1500 km. In March 2011, the

“Agreement on Cooperation in Transporting and Transiting Goods between Pakistan and Uzbekistan” was signed, and new opportunities for transit through Afghanistan would open up if the situation in Afghanistan stabilizes.

1-image. Annual change in transit cargo (million tons)

Uzbekistan has played a positive role in diversifying the direction of external trade cargo transportation for transit through the ports of Afghanistan, Iran, and Pakistan.

In Uzbekistan, significant attention is being paid to the development of mainline railway communications to enhance the country's transit capabilities. The completion of the Navoiy-Uchquduq-Sultonuzdog railway line, spanning 341 km, in 2001, and the Toshguzar-Boysun-Qumqorgon line, covering 220 km, in 2007, serve as solid evidence of this commitment.

In November 2010, the construction of the first railway in Afghanistan, the Hayraton-Mazar-i-Sharif railway, with a length of 75 km, was completed, marking a significant event for the entire Central Asian region. This project was implemented under the auspices of the Organization for Transport and Communications of the

Economic Cooperation Organization (ECO), and it was executed by the “Uzbekistan Railways” state joint-stock company.

Railway transportation plays a crucial role in meeting the needs of the population, conducting economic activities, operating the transport system, and developing the transportation market in Uzbekistan. Like in many other countries, the export and transit of goods bring significant economic benefits to Uzbekistan. Therefore, the “Uzbekistan Railways” joint-stock company is developing long-term strategic plans. The main goal of the Concept for the Development of Railway Transportation in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2024 is to ensure the sustainable socio-economic development of the country, improve the well-being of the population, and create conditions for the development of railway transportation. The positions of the Republic of Uzbekistan are based on the innovative development of railway transportation. One of the ways to achieve these goals is to develop railway routes and enhance the country's transit capabilities.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the current state of railway transit movement dynamics is as follows: The adoption of modern transportation system technologies has led to an increase in the transportation of goods by railway in Uzbekistan. Transport regulation, flexible trade agreements, and adjusting the weight and dimensions of transport vehicles contribute to addressing unresolved issues in the industry. Railway transportation gains competitive strength among other modes of transport within these changes.

Between 1995 and 2010, the Republic of Uzbekistan formulated a national development strategy aimed at enhancing its position in Central Asia, fostering industrial and other sectoral advancements, and intensifying economic relations with neighboring states. Within this strategy, construction began on the “Qamchiq” and “Rezak” tunnels on sections of the “Tashkent–Andijan–Osh” mainline railway that exceed 100 km. Repairs were conducted on sections of the “Olma-ota–Bishkek–Tashkent–Termiz” and “Samarkand–Bukhara–Ashgabat–Turkmenbashi” highways passing through the territory of the republic. Furthermore, the construction of the

340-kilometer “Qongirot–Beyneu” highway linking Uzbekistan with the Russian Federation through Kazakhstan was completed via Uzbekistan's connection with Kazakhstan.

2-image. Block diagram of the stages of corridor freight traffic development in railway transportation

In order to continue the development of construction activities in the Republic, a program to significantly enhance the construction of transportation and communication infrastructure from 2011 to 2015 was adopted. This program provided further opportunities for the development of the country's and regions' economies by implementing projects related to transportation and engineering-communication infrastructure. According to this program, in 2012, approximately 500 kilometers of modern four-lane highways were constructed and reconstructed.

Central Asia is considered an integral part of the global transportation and communication system. In this regard, Uzbekistan has undertaken extensive efforts to modernize its transportation infrastructure and open up new international routes.

In our country, strategic directions have been outlined for the development of the electrified railway network. In this regard, from 1994 to 2001, the “Navoi-Uchquduq-Nukus” railway line, with a length of nearly 700 kilometers, was constructed. As a result, this railway line has facilitated the transportation of various goods to the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the Khorezm region since its early years of operation.

Conclusion

In furtherance of enhancing the railway network in the Republic, the new “Guzar-Boysun-Qumqorgon” railway was constructed. On August 24, 2007, during the grand opening of the “Toshguzar-Boysun-Qumqorgon” railway, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, emphasized, “The modern railway lines, through the rocks of the mountains and the fields of the valleys, have been built with the diligent labor of our people under the sun, and the commissioning of this 223-kilometer railway line in a short period, all in just 33 months, two years ahead of schedule, is undoubtedly a significant event in the history of our country, a comprehensive and remarkable event.”

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